

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #5

EV Battery Analysis:

Insights for Recycling and Second-Life Use

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Executive Summary

Figure 15. Electric vehicle battery analysis: Insights for recycling and second-life use - Graphical Abstract.

The case study examines the growth potential of used electric vehicles in the UK market, addressing industry trends, the factors influencing second-life electric vehicle battery expansion, and opportunities and challenges in the reconditioned electric vehicle market. Results emphasize the importance of expanding charging infrastructures and establishing battery repurposing/recycling facilities to

stimulate the second-hand electric vehicle market. Recommendations include collaboration with major manufacturers, strategic planning for popular car models, continued analysis of market trends, and the adoption of battery recycling and health assessment practices to capitalize on the expanding used electric vehicle market.

Abstract

This executive summary provides an insightful overview of a comprehensive survey assessing the prevalence and potential growth of used electric vehicle (EV) batteries in the UK market. The investigation explores industry trends, factors influencing second-life EV battery expansion, and opportunities and challenges in the reconditioned EV market.

The analysis employed a robust system, examining EV market trends, battery advancements, and government policies, drawing data from reputable

secondary sources and the UK vehicle registration database. To estimate the prevalence of used EV batteries in the UK, various forecasting methods, including regression analysis and pattern extrapolation, were utilized. However, it is crucial to acknowledge the inherent risks and assumptions involved in forecasting based on existing market patterns. Nonetheless, the application of these approaches enabled a comprehensive understanding of the potential appearance of used EV batteries in the UK market.

Findings project a promising 87% increase in the second-hand EV market from 2022 to 2025, driven by EV adoption, government incentives, and interest in sustainable transportation. The regulatory environment in the UK, characterized by cash incentives, tax reductions, and substantial investments in charging infrastructure, emerged as a crucial catalyst in supporting the growth of the used EV industry. Furthermore, technological advancements in battery innovation and recycling methods were identified as pivotal factors contributing to the viability and appeal of used EVs. These advancements are anticipated to lead to longer battery life spans and reduced environmental impact, rendering used EVs an attractive and eco-friendly alternative for users.

The study also highlighted the escalating demand for affordable EVs within the used car market, offering users a cost-effective option to embrace sustainable transportation. The growth of

charging infrastructure and the establishment of battery repurposing and recycling facilities were identified as instrumental drivers behind the expansion of the second-life EV market. Furthermore, there are ongoing efforts to further enhance the charging network and promote eco-responsible practices throughout the entire EV lifecycle, reinforcing the sustainability of the used EV industry.

In conclusion, this study offers valuable insights into the emerging used EV battery market in the UK, addressing market size, battery diversity, utilization, and lucrative second-life EV prospects, guiding stakeholders towards a sustainable automotive landscape.

Introduction

The primary objective of this research paper was to forecast and estimate the influx of used electric vehicle (EV) batteries into the rapidly growing UK market. The study delved into current industry trends and the various factors influencing the growth of second-life EV batteries, with a particular focus on providing valuable insights into the expected trends and opportunities within the

country's expanding market for used EVs.

In this context, Battery Cycle emerges as a leading company that specializes in the management, repurposing, and recycling of EV batteries. As the demand for EVs continues to surge in the UK market, the need for efficient and sustainable battery solutions becomes increasingly critical. Battery Cycle plays a vital role in addressing this need, offering innovative and responsible battery lifecycle management services. The significance of EV batteries within the context of the UK's transportation sector cannot be overstated. As the country makes strides toward reducing greenhouse gas emissions and advancing the transition to a low-carbon economy, the proper handling and utilization of EV batteries become paramount. Battery Cycle's approach aligns seamlessly with the UK government's commitment to sustainability, as their services contribute to the circular economy, promoting responsible resource utilization.

Through their battery repurposing and recycling initiatives, Battery Cycle not only extends the useful life of EV batteries but also ensures their proper disposal at the end of their lifecycle. By doing so, they actively minimize the environmental impact of these batteries, further bolstering the UK's efforts to promote a greener and more sustainable future. As the demand for EVs continues to rise, the responsible management and utilization of second-life EV batteries will play a crucial role in shaping the future of the UK's electric mobility landscape. Battery Cycle's innovative approach to battery lifecycle management underscores their commitment to advancing sustainability and contributing to a cleaner and more environmentally friendly transportation sector.

The UK market for EVs has experienced remarkable growth in recent years, driven by various factors, including government incentives,

advancements in battery technology, and a rising environmental consciousness among consumers. According to the Society of Motor Manufacturers and Traders (SMMT, 2021), the sale of EVs in the UK reached a record high in 2020, with over 100,000 new registrations, signifying a substantial increase compared to previous years. As the quantity of EVs on UK roads continues to rise, the management of EV batteries becomes a basic concern. However, despite their limited lifespan for essential vehicle use, EV batteries still hold a significant measure of energy storage capacity, making them important for secondary applications. The Battery Cycle plays a crucial job in broadening the existence of EV batteries by repurposing them for different purposes, such as stationary energy storage systems (Y. Wang et al., 2020). The repurposing of EV batteries offers several benefits, including cost-effectiveness, an increased energy storage capacity, and a

reduced ecological footprint (Dunn et al., 2015). Through battery repurposing, Battery Cycle addresses the growing demand for energy storage solutions in the UK, facilitating the integration of renewable energy sources into the system and promoting a more sustainable energy infrastructure. As a sustainable and environmentally friendly transportation option, the transition to electric cars (EVs) has gained significant momentum in recent times. The breakthroughs in battery innovation, which are essential for increasing the driving reach, decreasing charging times, and eventually reassuring the mass reception of EVs, are at the core of this shift. This case study examines the present status of batteries used in electric vehicles, featuring significant technologies, problems, and prospective solutions. The case study opens with a careful clarification of the battery innovation frequently used in electric vehicles. It addresses lithium-particle

(Li-particle) batteries, the most well-known choice because of their high energy density, lightweight, and exceptionally low self-discharge rates. Also, it looks at state-of-the-art innovations that could totally disrupt the EV industry, such as lithium-sulfur batteries, solid-state batteries, and other non-traditional energy storage methods.

Two central concerns in the realm of EVs are their driving range and the infrastructure for charging. This section thoroughly examines the current state of battery innovation and its implications for the scope of EVs, covering essential aspects like battery capacity, energy density, and thermal management. Additionally, it delves into the challenges of expanding the ongoing charging infrastructure to meet the surging demand for fast and efficient charging options. Consumer confidence is profoundly influenced by the

performance and durability of EV batteries. Thus, this segment of the case study assesses the long-term reliability of batteries by scrutinizing factors such as temperature, charging cycles, and depth of discharge that impact battery health. Moreover, it explores various methods to extend battery life and mitigate capacity fading, including the implementation of battery management systems and cutting-edge charging algorithms. Top of FormBottom of Form

Description of Case Study

The ecological impact of battery manufacturing and disposal should not be overlooked, even as EVs help reduce greenhouse gas emissions during their use. To address waste and recover valuable materials for future battery production, this section investigates the environmental effects of battery manufacturing.

Despite the benefits of EVs, their widespread adoption is hindered by battery costs. The case study examines the economics of battery production, analyzing cost-influencing factors such as raw material costs, production methods, and economies of scale (Etxandi-Santolaya et al., 2023). Additionally, it explores potential strategies to reduce battery costs and make EVs more affordable for consumers.

Moreover, Battery Cycle's commitment to EV battery recycling ensures the recovery of valuable raw materials and minimizes the environmental impact of the automotive industry. The recycling process involves the extraction and reuse of materials such as lithium, cobalt, and nickel, which are crucial components of EV batteries (Gaines, 2018). By employing environmentally responsible recycling practices, Battery Cycle helps reduce the reliance on mining for these essential materials, contributing to resource conservation and sustainability.

In conclusion, Battery Cycle plays a pivotal role in managing, repurposing, and recycling EV batteries in the UK market. With the ongoing rise in EV demand, Battery Cycle's services contribute significantly to the sustainability and efficiency of the transportation sector. By maximizing the value and lifespan of EV batteries, the company actively supports the circular economy and fosters responsible resource utilization. Battery Cycle's innovative approach aligns perfectly with the UK government's environmental objectives, highlighting the importance of sustainable battery solutions in the ever-evolving automotive landscape.

Case Study Solution

The research project forecasts second-life electric vehicle (EV) numbers in the UK, evaluating economic, environmental, and technological aspects of second-life EV batteries. Data was collected from diverse sources, including the government's vehicle registration database, industry reports, and expert consultations. The methodology involves statistical analysis, regression, and trend extrapolation. Advanced tools assess energy consumption, emissions, and economic viability. Performance evaluation of battery technologies and a comprehensive market study were conducted. The research aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders, promoting EV adoption, enhancing performance, and sustainability in the UK's dynamic market landscape.

Data Collection

The data collection process for this research project was extensive and involved gathering information from various primary and secondary sources. One of the primary data sources was the UK government's vehicle registration database, which provided essential data on the number of electric vehicles currently registered in the country (GOV.UK, 2023). This dataset was crucial for establishing a baseline and understanding the current state of the EV market in the UK.

In addition to official government data, the study also relied on secondary sources such as industry reports, research papers, and government publications. These sources offered valuable insights into the trends, challenges, and opportunities within the electric vehicle industry. Industry reports provided valuable market intelligence

and predictions for the future growth of EV adoption in the UK.

To enhance the accuracy and applicability of the study's findings, the research team conducted consultations with industry experts, battery providers, and other automakers. These interactions allowed the researchers to gain practical insights into the real-world performance of EV batteries and understand the challenges and opportunities in the electric vehicle market. Feedback from customers and end-users provided valuable information on battery types, capacities, charging infrastructure, and driving range, which further enriched the dataset.

Furthermore, the research project aimed to collaborate with leading electric vehicle and battery manufacturers, as well as pertinent governmental organizations. This collaboration was crucial for accessing current and reliable data related to battery chemistry, energy storage capability, degradation trends, and safety requirements.

By tapping into the expertise of these industry leaders, the research team could ensure that their analysis was based on up-to-date and accurate information.

Methodology

The research methodology followed a systematic and structured approach, starting with a comprehensive analysis of the collected data. During the analysis phase, the data underwent both statistical and qualitative analysis to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. Statistical techniques were used to identify trends and correlations within the data, while qualitative analysis helped to interpret and contextualize the findings.

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the input data, the research team employed advanced forecasting methodologies, including data pre-processing and cleaning. Data pre-processing involved identifying and addressing potential outliers and

inconsistencies within the dataset, ensuring that the subsequent analysis was based on reliable information (Colarullo & Thakur, 2022). By carefully handling the data, the researchers aimed to minimize the impact of data noise and improve the robustness of their analysis.

Regression analysis, a powerful statistical tool, was then applied to establish relationships between various variables and to derive meaningful insights regarding the arrival of used EVs in the UK market. This technique allowed the research team to model the relationships between different factors and understand how they might influence the growth of the second-life EV market.

Additionally, trend extrapolation was incorporated into the analysis to extend the findings into the future. By identifying historical patterns and trends, the researchers could project potential growth patterns in the industry. However, the research team acknowledges that forecasting inherently involves

uncertainties and assumptions based on prevailing market trends and conditions. As such, the results should be interpreted with caution, considering the dynamic and ever-changing nature of the market landscape.

Technology Employed

The research project leveraged sophisticated data gathering and analysis tools to gain valuable insights into the energy consumption, pollutant emissions, and economic viability of second-life EV batteries. Advanced software and mathematical algorithms were employed to process and analyze the vast amount of data collected from multiple sources.

Moreover, the research included a performance assessment of various battery technologies used in electric cars. This evaluation involved analyzing several important metrics, such as energy effectiveness, driving range, charging speed, and

temperature sensitivity. By assessing these performance indicators, the research team could determine the strengths and weaknesses of different battery technologies and their applicability in various electric vehicle types and driving situations.

The environmental impact of EV batteries was also a significant component of the study. A comprehensive examination was conducted, encompassing the entire lifecycle of the batteries - from the extraction of raw materials to the manufacturing processes, the usage phase, and eventual recycling. Understanding the environmental implications of EV batteries was vital for assessing their sustainability as a green transportation alternative.

Furthermore, the research incorporated a thorough market study to comprehend the current trends and potential futures for the use of electric vehicles. This analysis considered various factors, including government

regulations, incentives, customer preferences, and infrastructural advancements that could influence the growth of EV battery technologies in the UK market. By understanding these market dynamics, the research team aimed to develop a comprehensive forecast of the second-life EV market's potential growth and the challenges it might face.

In conclusion, the research project utilized a diverse array of data sources and advanced tools for data analysis, including sophisticated software and mathematical algorithms. The methodology employed a structured approach, involving statistical and qualitative analysis, regression analysis, and trend extrapolation to forecast the number of second life EVs in the UK market. The technology employed encompassed a performance assessment of EV batteries and a comprehensive market study to understand current trends and potential growth opportunities (Illa Font et al.,

2023). By combining these elements, the research team sought to provide valuable insights and well-informed recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders in the automobile sector, contributing to the adoption and improvement of electric vehicles in the UK.

Results and Discussion

The main aim of this project was to forecast and get an idea of no of EVs that will be available for second life use in the United Kingdom. For this purpose, we used a step-by-step procedure. We started analyzing them from the basics and worked our way towards the goal.

Analysis: It helps to gather knowledge about the possible effects of introducing second-life EV batteries, the data collected was statistically and qualitatively analyzed. This research focuses on the economic, environmental, and technological elements of SLBs to examine the possibilities for integrating them into the UK market. Due to its favourable environmental effects and decreased reliance on fossil fuels, EV adoption has been gradually rising in the UK. But as the EV industry expands, a problem with second-hand electric vehicle batteries (SLB) appears.

Market analysis: The present situation of the UK EV market was examined, including sales data, EV models, and charging

infrastructure. Data about SLB's accessibility and market integration were also looked at. With more EV models readily available to customers, the EV market in the UK has grown significantly over the past several years. SLBs are now more widely available as a result of breakthroughs in battery technology and recycling procedures. SLBs are a desirable alternative for energy storage applications since they are often less expensive than new batteries. Battery leasing, remanufacturing, and recycling are just a few of the several pathways via which SLB revenue streams might be produced.

In this, the first analysis was based on which are the top 10 EV manufacturers in the United Kingdom. For this, we used our main dataset from DVLA (Driver and Vehicle Licensing Agency).

Figure 16. Top 10 makes of EVs in the Parc

From Figure 16 we can see that BMW is currently dominating the EV market with 17% of the total EVs in the United Kingdom being manufactured by them which is followed by Tesla which is 17 %, which being a new company in the market is giving reliable results. Since our main aim is second life use of batteries this data is important because different EV manufacturers use different battery chemistry. This could even be useful to form partnerships with top

manufacturers to collaborate on second-life use of these batteries. To solidify this learning on the top manufacturers we next focused on forecasting this data towards 2030 and as we expected from Figure 17, we can see that Tesla overtook BMW in the EV race. For this analysis, we used a linear regression model. This graph helps us to focus on the future top manufacturers according to the trend.

Figure 17. Total EVs for each year by top 10 EV makers

Figure 18. EV registration by body type for each year (last 5 years)

According to manufacture and year, Figure 18 breaks down the total number of Electric vehicles on the market. Considering the exception of Mitsubishi, whose sales are declining, we can observe that all EV manufacturers are helping the growth. In the EV industry, Tesla saw a startling upswing in 2018 t

that just continued to grow. As seen in Figure 3, all EV manufacturers had a sharp increase in EV registrations in 2019 notwithstanding Covid's impact. This is in addition to how other manufacturers turned their attention to EVs after TESLA's success.

Figure 19. EV registrations by body type in 2023

The car type that has dominated the EV market in the UK during the past five years is seen in Figure 19. Cars are certainly dominating to a significant degree, as can be shown. These forces need to concentrate more of the research on automobiles, and

as there are far less of the other kind of vehicles, one could even try to discount them from it. Assessing whether second-hand EV batteries are appropriate for a particular use case is going to be made easier by understanding the body type.

Figure 20. Total EV by year of construction

The number of registered EVs overall is shown in Figure 20 by year. Up to 2018, one should expect a continuous rise. A major shift in the EV industry is anticipated after 2018. As the tendency continues to rise, the overall number of dead batteries is going to increase in

the upcoming years, as can be seen from the trend (Y. Wang et al., 2020). To understand market trends and make appropriate plans, use this data. As only facts up to the third quarter of 2022 are taken into account, the year might be judged as having less potential.

Figure 21. A representation of the cumulative battery capacity of different models

The total battery capacity of the various EV models now on the UK market is shown in Figure 21. To understand the raw resources that are accessible, this information is helpful. MWh is the battery's capacity. One

can see that the Tesla Model 3 currently on the market has a capacity of 5000MWh. Depending on the kind of battery, this information can later be transformed to determine the raw components.

Figure 22. A representation of the composition of different materials in batteries of electric vehicles

Now, one can see in Figure 22 how the raw materials are split by the EV model in kilograms. This information is crucial since it aids in properly planning the recycling process. Additionally, it is going to encourage the recovery of valuable materials and help decrease waste (Dunn

et al., 2015). Graphite has the highest concentration, followed by lithium, as can be shown. Knowing the battery's economic worth can also be aided by this. For this, we used a conventional ratio of 185 kg of minerals to 60 kwh of battery power.

Figure 23. Total distance driven for the top the 10 EV models

The lowest and highest mileage values for the top 10 EV vehicles are displayed in Figure 23. Depending on the current mileage, this information might be used to evaluate the

condition of the vehicle. They used years as a criterion for determining the State of health because we lacked access to any form of mileage data.

Figure 24. A representation of predicted number of EVs by year and battery health

The Predicted State of Health and the number of automobiles is shown in Figure 24 for each year. The battery is regarded as dead and frequently requires replacement if the state of health (SoH) is less than 80%. In light of this, we can estimate the number of EVs that will be available for usage in aftermarket applications by 2030. One million EV batteries would be accessible in the UK alone for reuse, according to the estimates. To forecast this, we employed a linear regression model. We started with an 80% SOH level and worked our way up to higher than 90% by considering the typical battery life of EVs, which is 8 years.

Researchers looked at a variety of factors in this study, starting with the fundamentals of leading manufacturers and ending with the State of health. The batteries for electric vehicles that are now on the market and those that are no longer suitable for use in vehicles but still have some powers were also a major

emphasis. In this study, researchers looked at the UK market's size, the various EV battery types that are offered, and the use of repurposed EV batteries (Thorne et al., 2021). The EV battery's capacity, lifespan, and deteriorating process were also considered.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Recommendations

The market for used electric vehicles offers substantial opportunity for vehicle manufacturers, dealerships, and other stakeholders to capitalize on the growing desire for inexpensive and sustainable transportation options. These suggestions are meant to help your company be ready for the arrival of second-life electric vehicle (EV) batteries, including looking into partnerships, making infrastructure investments, and thinking about marketing plans.

To handle the growing influx of old electric vehicle (EV) batteries, the company needs to invest in the creation of a strong infrastructure for battery recycling. The company should create recycling facilities with cutting-edge technology so that it can safely remove valuable materials and safely dispose of dangerous waste.

An alternative to recycling old batteries is to reuse them in order to extend their usable life. Energy storage systems are

among the main areas where used batteries are put to use. The extra renewable energy produced by sources like solar or wind power can be stored in large-scale storage systems made from the combined use of these batteries. These systems can offer electricity at times of high demand and also help to smooth out variations in the power supply by storing extra energy.

In order to increase economic benefits, it is imperative to create an infrastructure for an electrical grid based on EV rapid charging stations and second-life battery energy storage devices. The infrastructure for electric vehicle charging can be supported by repurposed EV batteries. These batteries can be used for energy storage to regulate peak charging demand, balance power loads, and ease the burden on the electrical grid.

We encourage cooperation with EV producers to make it easier to recycle and reuse second life batteries. EV

manufacturers should develop collaboratively effective and standardized battery collection, testing, refurbishing, and recycling procedures.

Encourage automakers to assume accountability for the end-of-life management of their goods.

We recommend that EV manufacturers should support activities in research and development that are centred on battery recycling and other second-life uses. Investigate novel applications for retired EV batteries, such as stationary power sources, energy storage devices, or grid stabilizing techniques. To promote innovation in this area, establish collaborations with research facilities, academic institutions, and business leaders.

The company should create standardized techniques to evaluate the state of used EV batteries and their remaining capacity. Adopt stringent testing techniques to evaluate battery performance, deterioration rates, and appropriateness for reusing in other applications. It is advised

to use cloud-connected storage solutions to monitor battery aging during the whole life cycle.

The organization can work with the government to disseminate information to the general public about the value of recycling old EV batteries and disposing of them properly. Convey the possible economic and environmental advantages of recycling activities. To promote sensible battery management, provide information about collection locations, recycling facilities, and accessible aftermarket applications.

In addition, EV manufacturers can establish recycling facilities and pickup stations for used EV batteries in cooperation with local authorities. Make sure there are handy and easily accessible sites where customers may return their batteries. Start local awareness campaigns to encourage battery recycling and repurposing efforts.

The company can participate in global partnerships and knowledge-sharing forums to share top battery recycling and repurposing techniques. Utilize the knowledge of nations with well-established battery recycling programs and learn from them to help the UK advance more quickly.

The organization should keep an eye on the success of activities for recycling and reusing batteries. Analyse the effectiveness and efficiency of various strategies. Review and revise your strategies frequently in light of new developments in technology, market trends, business prospects and new possibilities (Cusenza et al., 2019)c.

Used batteries can be incorporated into off-grid power systems, which are useful in places like isolated or rural areas without access to dependable electrical networks. For off-grid communities or installations, these batteries can provide a sustainable and dependable power supply by storing renewable energy

produced from sources like solar or wind power.

The company should keep up to date with regulatory and policy changes related to EVs and second life batteries in the UK. This can include changes to tax incentives, grants, and subsidies, as well as environmental regulations that may impact battery recycling and refurbishing processes.

The UK government should roll out financial rewards and assistance programs to promote recycling and reusing old EV batteries. Companies engaged in battery recycling or repurposing projects should be offered grants or tax incentives (Hossain et al., 2019). Donate money to research and development projects aimed at increasing the effectiveness of battery recycling and reusing.

For the smooth processing, recycling, and disposal of second-life EV batteries, specific rules and regulations

need to be established by the UK government. There must be measures in place to ensure that environmental regulations are followed at all stages of the battery life cycle, including collecting, transportation, and processing.

The company can manage the influx of used EV batteries, reduce environmental effects, advance the circular economy, and realize the potential value of these batteries beyond their primary use in EVs by putting these ideas into practice (Iqbal et al., 2023). In order to build a general economic model, it is advised that consideration be given to future price inflation, correct battery market pricing, and net metering rates.

Conclusion

Based on an examination of market patterns and available data, the research predicts that the arrival of used EV batteries in the UK market will expand steadily over the next five years. The increased adoption of electric vehicles in the UK is likely to increase demand for used EV batteries.

Furthermore, rising demand for energy storage solutions, especially in the renewable energy industry, has resulted in a developing market for used EV batteries. By incorporating these recommendations into strategic planning and decision-making processes, stakeholders can leverage the findings from the project to maximize the potential of the second-life EV market, contribute to sustainability goals, and establish a robust and circular economy in the EV sector.

Collaboration with Leading

Manufacturers: Establish partnerships with top EV manufacturers, such as BMW and Tesla, to explore opportunities for collaboration in the second-life use of their batteries. This can involve repurposing partnerships, joint research and development projects, and resource sharing.

Geographic Focus:

Concentrate efforts and resources on England, the region with the highest

concentration of EVs. Develop tailored strategies and initiatives to promote second-life EV programs, charging infrastructure expansion, and recycling facilities to maximize impact and benefits.

Strategic Planning: Prioritize the analysis and planning of second-life EV initiatives for car models, considering their dominance in the market.

Develop specific use cases and applications for second-life EV batteries in the automotive sector, such as electric vehicle fleets or ride-sharing programs.

Market Trend Analysis:

Continuously monitor market trends and industry developments to adapt strategies and forecast future demand for second-life EV batteries accurately. Regularly update forecasting models based on updated data and industry insights.

Recycling and Resource

Recovery: Encourage the development and implementation of efficient and environmentally responsible recycling processes for EV

batteries. Promote the recovery of valuable raw materials, such as graphite and lithium, to minimize waste and maximize resource utilization.

Battery Health Assessment:

Develop tools and methodologies to assess the health and remaining lifespan of EV batteries accurately. Consider factors beyond mileage, such as years of use, to determine the State of Health (SoH) and identify batteries suitable for second-life applications.

In conclusion, we highlight the need to keep an eye on market trends and adjust strategy as the industry changes.

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